

Indian Automobile Industry: Opportunity Threat and Challenge

Satyendra Kumar¹, Mamta Rawat² & S. K. Srivastava³

1. Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce, Govt. P.G. College New Tehri, Tehri Garhwal, Uttarakhand, Email: satyendra.inc@gmail.com
2. Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce, Govt. PG College New Tehri, Tehri Garhwal, Uttarakhand, Email: m.rawatkvs@gmail.com
3. Professor (retid.), Department of Commerce, HNB Garhwal University, Srinagar Garhwal, Uttarakhand, Email: dr.santosh.srivastava@gmail.com

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Abstract

In 2020, India was the fifth-largest auto market, with 3.49 million units combined sold in the passenger and commercial vehicles categories. It was the seventh largest manufacturer of commercial vehicles in 2019 and employs around 32 million people. The two wheelers segment dominates the market in terms of volume owing to a growing middle class and a young population. Moreover, the growing interest of the companies in exploring the rural markets further aided the growth of the sector. The industry attracted Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) worth US\$ 25.40 billion between April 2000 and December 2020. The Indian automotive industry is expected to reach US\$ 300 billion by 2026. The March 2020 numbers show the effect of lockdown due to the COVID-19 pandemic and switch from Bharat Stage 4 (BS4) to Bharat Stage 6 (BS6) emission norms has also negative impact of automobile industry. In the present study an attempt has been made to show the impact of covid-19 and technological changes in automobile industry. In order to meet the challenges posed by pandemic the Indian automobile manufacturers need to ensure the technological advancement, appropriate marketing strategies and adequate customer care feedback system in their organizations.

Key words: Foreign Direct Investment, Covid-19 Pandemic, Lockdown, BS4, BS6.

Introduction:

The first car ran on India's roads in 1897. Until the 1930s, cars were imported directly. Embryonic automotive industry emerged in India in the 1940s. Following the independence, in 1947, the government of India and the private sector launched efforts to create an automotive component manufacturing industry to supply to the automobile industry. However, the growth was relatively slow in the 1950s and 1960s due to nationalization and the license raj which hampered the Indian private sector. After 1970, the automotive industry started to grow, but the growth was mainly driven by tractors, commercial vehicles and scooters. Cars were still a major luxury. Japanese manufacturers entered the Indian market ultimately leading to the establishment of Maruti Udyog. A number of foreign firms initiated joint ventures with Indian companies.

In the 1980s, a number of Japanese manufacturers launched joint-ventures for building motorcycles and light commercial-vehicles. It was at this time that the Indian government chose Suzuki for its joint-venture to manufacture small cars. After Economic Liberalisation in India in 1991, the Indian automobile industry has demonstrated sustained growth as a result of increased competitiveness and relaxed restrictions. Several Indian automobile manufacturers such as Tata Motors, Maruti Suzuki and Mahindra & Mahindra expanded their domestic and international operations. India's robust economic growth led to the further expansion of its domestic automobile market which attracted significant India-specific investment by multinational automobile manufacturers. In February 2009, monthly sales of passenger cars in India exceeded 100,000 units. As of 2009, 40 million passenger vehicles and more than 1.5 million cars were sold in India in 2009 (an increase of 26%). It refers India

as the second fastest growing automobile market in the world. In 2020, India was the fifth-largest auto market, with 3.49 million units combined sold in the passenger and commercial vehicles categories. It was the seventh largest manufacturer of commercial vehicles in 2019 and employs around 32 million people. The total investment in this sector is around \$40 billion in the last decade. The decade of 2001-2010 saw a compounded annual sales growth of 15.67 per cent, which included 10 per cent exports. The yearly growth of exports was 23 per cent from 2000 to 2015 due to constant government support. By 2050, the country is expected to top the world in car volumes with approximately 611 million vehicles on the nation's roads. A major chunk of India's car manufacturing industry is based in and around the city of Chennai, with the Indian city accounting for 60 per cent of the country's automotive exports. Chakan corridor near Pune, Maharashtra is another prominent vehicular production hub with General Motors, Volkswagan/Skoda, Mahindra and Mahindra in the process of setting up or already set up facilities. Halol in Gujarat, Gurgaon neighboring New Delhi, Aurangabad in Maharashtra, Kolkatta in West Bangal are some of the other automotive manufacturing regions around the country.

The March 2020 numbers show the effect of lockdown due to the COVID-19 pandemic. The industry produced a total 22,652,108 vehicles in April-March 2021 as against 26,353,293 in April-March 2020, registering a de-growth of (-) 14.04 percent over the same period last year. Sale of Three Wheelers declined by (-) 66.06 percent in April-March 2021 over the same period last year. Within the Three Wheelers, Passenger Carrier and Goods Carrier declined by (-).74.49 percent and (-) 26.38 percent respectively in April-March 2021 over April-March 2020. In April-March 2021, overall automobile exports declined by (-) 13.05 percent. Passenger Vehicles, Commercial Vehicles, Three Wheelers and Two Wheelers exports also declined by (-) 38.92 percent, (-) 16.64 percent, (-) 21.67 percent, and (-) 6.87 percent respectively. On the other hand technological change like leapfrogging to BS-VI norms, 100% EVs by 2030, GST, ELV policy, methanol economy, fuel efficiency norms, alternate fuels have posed several challenges in terms of technology up-gradation, investment, affordability, implementation etc.,

Literature Review

There are number of research studies undertaken on Indian Automobile industry for example A. Mukherjee, T. Sasty (1996); discussed about the future expected growth, Infrastructure requirements, demand estimation investment requirement and government regulation in automobile industry. N. Biswajit, B. Saikat, C. Rittwik (2007), the study examines the growth patterns, changes in ownership structures, trade patterns and role of governments of selected Asian countries (viz. China, India, Indonesia and Thailand) in the automobile sector. Dr. Govind P. Shinde Dr. Manisha Dubey (2011) The study represents the figures of Indian Automobile Industry during the period 2005to 2010. The study has been conducted considering the segments such as passenger vehicle, commercial vehicle, utility vehicles, multi-purpose, two wheelers and three wheelers. Each section concisely explains the current and future market trends, and developments in the Indian automobile market. Dr. Ankur Kumar Rastogi, Nitin Gopal Gupta (2013), discuss about the slowdown in Indian automobile industry the study period is 2005-06 to 2012-13. Dr. Anubha Srivastava (2014) analyze and compare the performance of the index securities of the leaders in the various segments of the automobiles and also find out the extent of relationships between auto sector index with the market index. Dr. C. Gopalakrishnan (2014), analyze and compare the segment wise (Two-wheeler, Passenger vehicle, commercial vehicle and three wheelers) contribution and trend of the sector. Neelofar Kamal, (2017) discuss the major objectives behind the Make in India initiative are job creation and skill enhancement and FDI inflows under the approval route (which requires prior government permission). Amima Shoeb, Adeel Maqbool (2017), The article will identify growth factor and significant factors that have led to the growth of automobile industry. It will help to indentify the contribution of other states that have led to the growth of automobile industry globally. Dr. Raju. V Dr.Vinay Kumar, N V Mahesh (2020), discuss about to understand requirements of the consumer from the automobile industry.

Research Gap: A comprehensive review of literature has been done on the Indian automobile industry through various sources such as books, journals, articles, research paper, etc. It has been founded that several studies have been conducted on various aspects of automobile industry but the impact of covid-19 on automobile industry is still not adequately addressed. So, this research paper will focus on the impact of covid-19 on automobile industry and try to find out how to cope-up with such pandemic situation.

Purpose of the Study:

- To examine the growth of Indian automobile industry in last decade(2011-12 to 2020-21)
- To find out the reasons of slowdown in Indian automobile industry.
- To find out the future growth, opportunity and challenges of Indian automobile industry.

Research Methodology and Limitations:

The present study is descriptive study. The analysis is based on Secondary data collected from various organizational databases, websites, newspapers and other necessary official records, books & magazines and Society of Indian Automobile Manufacturers (SIAM). In this study the processed data is related to years from 2011-12 to 2020-21. The data for the year 2019-20 and 2020-21 specially shows the impact of lockdown due to covid-19 pandemic. Statistical measures like Growth rate, % Change have been used to find out the conclusion. Besides Tables & Charts are used to present and analyze data.

Data Analysis:

The production of Indian automobile industry is shown year wise from 2011-12 to 2020-21 in different categories i.e. passenger vehicles, commercial vehicles, three wheelers and two wheelers. The growth rate in passenger vehicles segment in 2018-19 is 28.05 percent but due to the national wise lockdown it reduces 9.15 in 2019-20 and (-) 2.67 in 2020-21. Similarly commercial vehicles segment registered growth rate of 19.72 in 2018-19 and in 2020-21 it registered negative growth rate i.e. (-) 32.74 percent, in three wheelers segment maintain positive growth rate 44.30 till 2018-19 but after that it come down 28.95 in 2019-20 and become negative (-) 30.49 in 2020-21. In case of two wheelers segment growth rate of 58.81 percent in 2018-19 fall down 18.94 percent in 2020-21. During the study period overall growth rate is 11.12 percent in Indian automobile production.

Years	Category				Grand Total	% Change
	Passenger Vehicles	Commercial Vehicles	Three Wheelers	Two Wheelers		
2011-12	31,46,069	9,29,136	8,79,289	1,54,27,532	2,03,82,026	
2012-13	32,31,058	8,32,649	8,39,748	1,57,44,156	2,06,47,611	1.30
2013-14	30,87,819	6,99,035	8,30,108	1,68,83,049	2,15,00,011	4.13
2014-15	32,21,419	6,98,298	9,49,019	1,84,89,311	2,33,58,047	8.64
2015-16	34,65,045	7,86,692	9,34,104	1,88,30,227	2,40,16,068	2.82
2016-17	38,01,670	8,10,253	7,83,721	1,99,33,739	2,53,29,383	5.47
2017-18	40,20,208	8,95,448	10,22,181	2,31,54,838	2,90,92,675	14.86
2018-19	40,28,471	11,12,405	12,68,833	2,44,99,777	3,09,09,486	6.24
2019-20	34,34,013	7,52,022	11,33,858	2,10,36,294	2,63,56,187	-14.73
2020-21	30,62,221	6,24,939	6,11,171	1,83,49,941	2,26,48,272	-14.07
Growth Rate	-2.67	-32.74	-30.49	18.94	11.12	

Source: Society of Indian Automobile Manufacturers (SIAM)

The industry produced a total 2,26,48,272 vehicles including Passenger Vehicles, Commercial Vehicles, Three Wheelers and Two Wheelers in April-March 2021 as against 26,356,187 in April-March 2020, registering a negative-growth of (-) 14.07 percent over the same period last year.

The year wise consecutive percentage change in Indian automobile production trend has been shown in above graph 1. The industry is showing positive percent growths from 2011-12 to 2018-19. A negative percentage change in production came into existence during year 2019-20 and 2020-21 due to worldwide covid-19 impact. Otherwise during remaining study period a positive percentage change in production is extracted from the study. The year 2017-18 shows a little recovery in the production phase and after that a remarkable percentage change in automobile production (14.86%) found in 2017-18.

Automobile domestic sales trend has been shown in table no.2 in different categories from 2011-12 to 2020-21. In passenger vehicles segment the average growth rate is 3.10 percent in last decade. In commercial vehicles segment the growth rate is (-) 29.76 percent while from 2011-12 to 2018-19 it shown positive growth rate i.e. 24.44. Three wheelers segment is the most effected segment in terms of domestic sales trend in 2018-19 it registered growth rate of 36.57 percent but after that it's drastically reduce 24.02 in 2019-20 and (-) 57.88 percent in 2020-21. Two wheelers segment registered positive growth rate during the study period but it also showing decreeing trend of growth rate like 57.95 in 2018-19, 29.89 in 2019-20 and 12.75 in 2020-21. During this period the overall growth rate in all segments is 7.22 percent.

Years	Category				Grand Total	% Change
	Passenger Vehicles	Commercial Vehicles	Three Wheelers	Two Wheelers		
2011-12	2629839	809499	513281	13409150	17361769	
2012-13	2665015	793211	538290	13797185	17793701	2.49
2013-14	2503509	632851	480085	14806778	18423223	3.54
2014-15	2601236	614948	532626	15975561	19724371	7.06

2015-16	2789208	685704	538208	16455851	20468971	3.78
2016-17	3047582	714082	511879	17589738	21863281	6.81
2017-18	3288581	856916	635698	20200117	24981312	14.26
2018-19	3377381	1007311	701005	21179847	26265544	5.14
2019-20	2773575	717688	636569	17417616	21545448	-17.97
2020-21	2711457	568559	216197	15119387	18615600	-13.60
Growth Rate	3.10	-29.76	-57.88	12.75	7.22	

Source: Society of Indian Automobile Manufacturers (SIAM)

The overall consecutive (2011-12 is base year) percentage change in automobile domestic sales trends is been depicted in the graph 2. It shows a clear picture of covid-19 impact on Indian automobile industry. During the period of first five years the overall consecutive percentage change in domestic sales was 13 to 16 percent. The consecutive change in growth of domestic sales remains negative (-4.64%) in 2007-08. which was due to global crises phenomena. A slightly change was found in 2008-09 (i.e. 0.72%) in the Indian automobile industry. Which was progressing well upto 2006-07 came in the position of negative growth due to world wide recession. After the period of two years of global recession in 2009-10 it recovered upto 26.41 percent. It shows the clouds of global recession have become disappeared from Indian automobile industry.

Export trends of Indian automobile industry in different segments have been shown in table no. 3. In this table passenger vehicles segment the growth rate is (-) 20.52 percent.

Years	Category				Grand Total	% Change
	Passenger Vehicles	Commercial Vehicles	Three Wheelers	Two Wheelers		
2011-12	508783	92258	361753	1975111	2937905	
2012-13	559414	80027	303088	1956378	2898907	-1.33

2013-14	596142	77050	353392	2084000	3110584	7.30
2014-15	621341	86939	407600	2457466	3573346	14.88
2015-16	653053	103124	404441	2482876	3643494	1.96
2016-17	758727	108271	271894	2340277	3479169	-4.51
2017-18	748366	96865	381002	2815003	4041236	16.16
2018-19	676192	99933	567683	3280841	4624649	14.44
2019-20	677311	60713	502169	3520376	4760569	2.94
2020-21	404400	50334	392941	3277724	4125399	-13.34
Growth Rate	-20.52	-45.44	8.62	65.95	40.42	

Source: Society of Indian Automobile Manufacturers (SIAM)

During the period of 2011-12 to 2020-21 the growth rate of commercial vehicles segment is (-) 45.44 percent, in three wheelers categories the growth rate is comparatively highest i.e. 8.62 percent. The export position in two wheelers categories is also remarkable the growth rate in this segment is 65.95 percent. The overall growth rate in automobile export remains 40.42 percent. The consecutive change is shown in last column in table no 3.

The above picture has shown a percent change in consecutive automobile export trends. In the year 2017-18 it was highest i.e. 16.16 percent. During this pandemic period it shows a decreasing trend from 2018-19 to 2020-21 the percentage in automobile export trends were 14.44%, 2.94%, and (-) 13.34% respectively. It shows a clear-cut covid-19 impact on our automobile exports. As a result our exports share in world market decreased. The combined effect of all the factors due to pandemic came in existence as a result shown a decreasing trend.

The present preview of Indian automobile industry as segment wise market share is shown in the following diagram. A largest share 81% of industry relates to two wheelers production. The market share of passengers' vehicles, commercial vehicles and three wheelers is 13%, 3% and 3% respectively.

Source: Society of Indian Automobile Manufacturers (SIAM)

Reasons of Downfall in Indian Automobile Industry:

On the basis of above analysis it is clearly shows that the Indian automobile industry was facing a deep structural slowdown since last two year. The year 2019-20 was one of the worst years for the automobile industry. We just try to find out some reason of downfall in Indian automobile industry:

BS6 Emission Standards

By April 2020, the BS6 emission norms will come into effect and all automobile manufacturers will have to upgrade their engine offerings accordingly. Not all automobile makers have clarified their position regarding the upcoming shift and how it will affect their product lineup that is offered to customers. As a result, certain buyers are delaying their new car purchase until there are more details available regarding BS6-compliant model choices.

New Insurance Norms

New insurance norms mandating third party insurance cover to be paid upfront for a period of three years for passenger vehicles and five years for two wheelers has raised on-road price for the respective segment for consumers - thereby impacting demand. The net outflow on account of premium payment will be more in the first year. Instead of making annual premium payments, the TP premium will have to be paid as an upfront-lump sum payment.

Oil Prices

Petrol and diesel prices do have an impact on the sale of automobile vehicles to some extent. The two are complementary products and therefore, there's always been some impact of petroleum prices on automobile sales. According to a study undertaken by E&Y in 2018, fuel cost accounts for 20-50 per cent of the cost of vehicle ownership in India, depending on distance travelled per day. The study assumes fuel cost of Rs 6 per kilometer, which has since increased.

Used Car Sales

The India used car market was valued at USD 27 billion in 2020, and it is expected to reach USD 50 billion by 20206, registering a CAGR of 15% during the forecast period, 2021-2026. The COVID-19 pandemic had a minimal impact on the industry. With the increased number of people preferring individual mobility and more finance options infused into the used car market, the market is set to grow considerably. Reduced cash inflow due to the pandemic has forced buyers to look for alternatives other than new cars, and the used car industry has great growth potential in these terms.

With the sales and production of new vehicles hindered due to the pandemic, the immediate option for the buyers is the used car market. The used car market evolved in the country, with the growth of the organized and semi-organized sales sectors. The pre-owned car market recorded sales of 4.4 million units in FY2020 as compared to only 2.8 million units of new passenger vehicles in the same year.

Financial Crisis

During covid-19 many people lost their jobs and due to nationwide lockdown reduce the income of individual. Due to this, sale of auto industry is going down. At Maruti Suzuki, the share of vehicles financed by loans fell to the lowest in three years at 77% of retail sales in the past two months. At two-wheeler maker Honda Motorcycle & Scooter India (HMSI), this fell 5 percentage points to 40% during May-June from the pre-covide period. According to people in the know, lenders used to allow an 8-10% relaxation on the minimum income required to give a certain amount of loan. But now, credit managers have been told to stick to the rule book. Pop-up advertisements on bank websites offering car and two-wheeler loans have also reduced significantly.

Opportunities and way forward:

The transformational regulatory policies in automotive sector have opened a new vista of opportunities to OEMs, auto components and auxiliary entities for developing new ecosystem and adapting to the newer regulatory policies. The paradigm shift in efficient and affordable transportation policies is providing opportunities for cementing new collaborations, partnerships, joint ventures, investments, transfer and development of cutting edge technologies in automobile sector. The new paradigm of low carbon transportation will encourage healthy competition from peers, R&D for innovations and advancement of technology including compliance to the national and international technical regulations to stay relevant and competitive. Make in India Initiatives and the faster adoption and manufacturing of electric and hybrid under the national electric mobility mission 2020 and 100% EVs by 2030. In addition, rapid urbanization, Smart cities programme, availability of raw material, cost effective capital, changing lifestyle etc. provide business supportive milieu and will foster new avenues of growth establishing completely new ventures and start-ups. India could be a leader in shared mobility by 2030, providing opportunities for electric and autonomous vehicles. Some other sign to future growth of automobile sector:

Growing demand

Rise in middle class income and young population may result in strong growth. Indian automobile industry is targeting to increase export of vehicles by five times during 2016-26. Indian automobile export stood at 14,19,430 units from April 2021 to June 2021. There are many who have already done pre-bookings for two-wheelers, cars and mini- SUVs to be picked on the October-November 2021. Mostly customers are opting to buy a four-wheeler which rang between Rs 6-8 lakh and automobile sector is expected to do a business of about Rs 25 crore this festive season.

Raising Investment

India has significant cost advantage. Auto firms save 10-25% on operations vis-à-vis Europe and Latin America. The automobile sector received cumulative FDI inflow of about US\$ 25.85 billion till March 2021. The government of India expects automobile sector to attract US\$ 8-10 billion in local and foreign investments by 2023.

Policy support

Automobile mission plan 2016-26 is a mutual initiative by the government of India and Indian Automobile industry to lay down the roadmap for development of the industry. The government aims to develop Indian as a global manufacturing centre. In union budget 2021-22, the government announced the voluntary vehicle scrappage policy to phase out old and unfit vehicles.

Conclusion:

The Automobile industry in India is one of the largest in the world and one of the fastest growing globally. The globalization process has affected the sector in all the areas of manufacturing, sales,

personnel research and development and financing. The automobile industry has a tremendous scope for growth in passenger cars and commercial vehicles. Above analysis clearly shows that, the impact of nation- wise lockdown on automobile industry. The automobile industry is supported by various factors such as availability of skilled labour at low cost, robust R&D centers and low cost steel production. The industry also provides great opportunities for investment and direct and indirect employment to skilled and unskilled labour. The Indian automobile industry is expected to record strong growth in 2021-22, post recovering from effects of Covid-19 pandemic. Electric vehicles, especially two-wheelers, are likely to witness positive sales in 2021-22. Some initiative taken by the government like, RBI special refinance facility of Rs. 50,000 crore was given to boost liquidity, validity of e-way bill was extended, moratorium period of 90 days for loan repayment was allowed, cut down the interest rate upto 6.50% boost up the automobile industry. The result reflected these initiative automobile sector is expected to do a business of about Rs 25 crore this festive season with advance booking of around 10 lakh four wheeler vehicles. Indian automobile industry is expected to reach Rs. 16.16-18.18 trillion by 2026.

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